

SEASONAL VARIATION OF BIOMOLECULES IN PLANT SPECIES:

Ragunathan Muthuswamy*¹ Anamika Sekar¹

¹Tamilnadu Dr.MGR. Medical University, Department of Pharmacognosy- PG studies, Swamy Vivekanandha College of Pharmacy, Tiruchengodu, Namakkal, Tamilnadu, India.

Abstract:

Background: Plants exhibit seasonal variations in their biochemical composition due to environmental factors such as temperature, light intensity, and soil moisture. These variations affect the levels of primary and secondary metabolites, which play crucial roles in plant growth, defence, and adaptation to changing climatic conditions.

Objective: This review gives information about seasonal variation in biomolecules, including carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, and secondary metabolites, in the plant species. It seeks to determine how different seasons influence biochemical composition and the potential implications for plant physiology, agriculture, and pharmacology.

Materials and Methods: This review is based on an extensive literature survey of peer-reviewed studies on seasonal variations in plant biomolecules. Data were collected from academic databases (PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar) using relevant keywords, focusing on studies employing analytical techniques like chromatography and spectrophotometry.

Discussion: Seasonal variation significantly influences the concentration and composition of biomolecules in plant species, affecting their growth, metabolism, and ecological interactions. This review synthesizes current findings on seasonal influences on plant biomolecules, discusses underlying physiological and environmental mechanisms, and highlights potential applications in plant-based industries.

Conclusion: This review highlights the impact of seasonal variations on plant biochemistry, providing insights for agricultural management, pharmaceutical applications, and ecological conservation. Understanding these fluctuations can help optimize plant resource utilization and enhance the quality of plant-derived products.

Keywords:Primary Metabolites, Secondary Metabolites, Environmental Factors, Seasonal Adaptation

Corresponding author:

Dr. Rangunathan Muthuswamy

Swamy Vivekanandha College of Pharmacy,

Tiruchengodu, Namakkal, Tamilnadu, India

1. Introduction

Due to environmental factors plants exhibit significant biochemical variations across different seasons such as temperature, light intensity, precipitation, and soil conditions. These fluctuations influence the synthesis and accumulation of primary and secondary metabolites, which play crucial roles in plant growth, development, and defence mechanisms [1]. Carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids are the primary metabolites essential for plant metabolism and energy storage. In contrast, Alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolics are the secondary metabolites that contribute to plant adaptation and resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses [2].

Seasonal changes significantly impact photosynthetic efficiency, nutrient uptake, and enzymatic activity, leading to variations in the concentration of metabolites[3]. For instance, during summer carbohydrate levels tend to peak due to enhanced photosynthesis, while during autumn and winter, secondary metabolites often accumulate in higher concentrations as part of the plant's stress response [4]. These biochemical shifts have profound implications for agriculture, medicinal plant harvesting, and ecological conservation, as they determine the nutritional and pharmaceutical value of plant-based products.

2. Biomolecules in plant and their seasonal variations:

Plants produce a wide range of biomolecules essential for their growth, development, and defence. The Primary and Secondary metabolites are the two types of biomolecules. Primary metabolites are directly involved in the growth and survival of the plant, while

secondary metabolites play crucial roles in ecological interactions, defence mechanisms, and adaptation to environmental changes.

2.1. Primary Metabolites:

Primary metabolites are compounds that are essential for plant lives and are universally present in all plant species. They are carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids. The most abundant biomolecules are plants **carbohydrates**, which are crucial in energy storage, transport, and structural integrity. Simple sugars like glucose and fructose are immediate energy sources, while starch and cellulose are the polysaccharides that provide energy storage and structural support [5]. Seasonal variations significantly impact carbohydrate content in plants. For example, during winter, deciduous trees store carbohydrates in their roots to survive dormancy, while in spring; these reserves are mobilized for new growth [6]. The macromolecules like Proteins are important in enzymatic activities, structural support, and metabolic functions. The proteins are composed of amino acids, which are influenced by seasonal changes. For instance, in cold climates, plants accumulate stress-related proteins such as heat shock proteins (HSPs) and antifreeze proteins (AFPs) to counteract environmental stress. Additionally, nitrogen availability, which fluctuates seasonally, affects protein synthesis, thereby influencing plant growth and development [7]. **Lipids** are also a type of Primary metabolites. Plant lipid composition changes with seasonal changes to maintain membrane fluidity and stability. During cold seasons, plants enhance unsaturated fatty acid content in membranes to maintain flexibility, whereas, in warmer seasons, saturated fatty acids are more prevalent [8]. Additionally, lipid-based signalling molecules such as jasmonic acid regulate plant responses to environmental stressors, including temperature fluctuations [9].

2.2. Secondary Metabolites:

Secondary metabolites are often species-specific and influenced by environmental factors such as light, temperature, and herbivory. Alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, and terpenoids are the major class of secondary metabolites.

Alkaloids are containing nitrogen as secondary metabolites essential for their pharmacological and ecological significance. They serve as chemical defenses against herbivores and pathogens. Many alkaloids exhibit seasonal changes in their concentration,

often peaking during stress conditions such as drought or cold. Due to herbivore activity nicotine in tobacco plants accumulates more in the summer [10]. Similarly, quinine and morphine levels in medicinal plants fluctuate with seasonal changes in environmental stressors [11]. **Flavonoids** are a diverse group of polyphenolic compounds that play roles in UV protection, pigmentation, and antioxidant activity. They are particularly responsive to seasonal variations in light intensity. Plants tend to accumulate higher flavonoid levels to counteract UV radiation in summer, while their synthesis is often reduced in winter. Flavonoids such as anthocyanins contribute to the red and purple hues seen in autumn leaves, which serve as a protective mechanism against oxidative stress [12]. Phenolic compounds include a broad range of bioactive molecules such as tannins, lignins, and coumarins. These compounds are involved in structural support (lignin), defense against herbivory (tannins), and allelopathic interactions. Seasonal changes influence phenolic content; for example, during the dry season higher levels of tannins are found in leaves to deter herbivores [13]. Phenolics also increase in response to environmental stress, such as drought or pathogen attack [14]. **Terpenoids** are the largest class of secondary metabolites, they are essential oils, resins, and plant hormones. This biomolecule contribute to plant defense and environmental adaptation. For example, monoterpenes in coniferous trees are more abundant in summer to protect against insect predation, while diterpenes accumulate in response to pathogen infections [15]. Terpenoid-based phytohormones, such as abscisic acid (ABA), play critical roles in drought tolerance and seasonal dormancy regulation [16].

3. Factors Influencing Seasonal Variation in Plant Biomolecules

Seasonal variations in biomolecules are primarily driven by environmental factors that influence plant metabolism, growth, and survival strategies. The factors are temperature, light intensity, water availability, soil nutrients, and photoperiodic cues. Understanding these influences is important for optimizing agricultural productivity, medicinal plant cultivation, and ecosystem sustainability.

3.1 Temperature

Temperature changes across seasons influence enzymatic activities, membrane stability, and metabolic pathways. Cold temperatures often lead to increased sugar accumulation to serve as cryoprotectants, enhancing frost resistance [17]. In contrast, higher temperatures

accelerate respiration, leading to increased metabolic turnover of carbohydrates and lipids [18]. Plants also adjust their secondary metabolites based on temperature fluctuations. For example, phenolic compounds and flavonoids are increased in response to cold stress, acting as antioxidants to mitigate oxidative damage [19]. Similarly, alkaloid biosynthesis is temperature-dependent, with certain alkaloids peaking in cooler seasons to enhance plant defense [20].

3.2 Light Intensity

For photosynthesis, light serves as the primary energy source and plays a crucial role in regulating plant biochemical pathways. Seasonal variations in light intensity and photoperiod affect both primary and secondary metabolism. High light intensity increases photosynthetic activity during summer, leading to higher carbohydrate synthesis [21]. Flavonoids and anthocyanins accumulate in response to high UV radiation, providing photoprotection and antioxidant benefits [12]. In shaded conditions (such as winter or dense canopies), plants may shift toward increased chlorophyll production to maximize light absorption [22].

3.3 Water Availability and Precipitation

Water is a fundamental requirement for plant survival, and seasonal variations in rainfall significantly impact metabolic processes. Drought conditions during dry seasons lead to increased accumulation of osmolytes such as proline, soluble sugars, and specific secondary metabolites like flavonoids and terpenoids to enhance drought tolerance [23]. Excess water from heavy rainfall can dilute cellular solutes, reducing concentrations of secondary metabolites like alkaloids, which are typically produced under stress conditions [1]. Water stress also influences hormonal regulation, particularly abscisic acid (ABA), which mediates stomatal closure and induces protective biochemical responses [16].

3.4 Nutrient Availability

High nitrogen availability promotes protein and amino acid synthesis, whereas low nitrogen triggers increased production of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids and phenolics [24]. Phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K) are essential for energy metabolism and

stress tolerance, their seasonal variation impacts the synthesis of key metabolites, including lipids and terpenoids [7].

3.5 Soil pH

Soil pH impacts nutrient solubility and microbial activity, thereby indirectly influencing plant metabolism. Acidic soils enhance the uptake of metal ions such as aluminum, which triggers oxidative stress and increases flavonoid synthesis [25]. Alkaline conditions can restrict nutrient availability, resulting in stunted growth and diminished metabolic activity [7]. Soil microbial communities also vary with the seasons, affecting nutrient cycling and plant health [26].

3.6 Photoperiod and Seasonal Cues

Photoperiod, or day length, is a vital environmental signal that regulates plant growth cycles, flowering, and secondary metabolism. In spring and summer, long-day plants (e.g., spinach and radish) initiate flowering as daylight increases, which is associated with changes in carbohydrate and hormone levels [27]. Conversely, short-day plants (e.g., rice and chrysanthemums) bloom as daylight wanes in autumn, often leading to increased production of alkaloids and phenolics to defend against cooler temperatures and herbivory [28]. Seasonal cues also regulate hormonal balances, such as increased **gibberellins (GAs)** during spring to promote stem elongation and flowering [29], Abscisic acid (ABA) levels increase during fall and winter to promote dormancy and enhance stress tolerance [16].

4. Seasonal Variations in Primary and Secondary Metabolites of plants:

Table 1: Seasonal variations in primary and secondary metabolites

S.NO	PLANT NAME	PRIMARY AND SECONDARY METABOLITES AFFECTED	SEASON OF PEAK ACCUMULATION	REFERENCE
1.	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Sugar, amino acids, Eugenol, ursolic acid	Summer	[30]
2.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Carbohydrates, Azadirachtin	Summer	[31]
3.	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	Carbohydrates, Menthol, Menthone	Spring	[32]

4.	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Proteins, Withanolides	Winter	[33]
5.	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Starch, curcumin	Summer	[34]
6.	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Vitamin c, Tannin, gallic acid	Winter	[35]
7.	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Sugars, vincristine, vinblastine	Summer	[36]
8.	<i>Aloe vera</i>	Polysaccharides, Aloin, anthroquinones	Winter	[37]
9.	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Carbohydrates, proteins, Gingerols	Winter	[38]
10.	<i>Andrographis Paniculata</i>	Glucose, Andrographolides	Rainy	[39]
11.	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Glucose, Bacosides	Summer	[40]
12.	<i>Eclipta alba</i>	Proteins, aminoacids, Wedelolactone	Rainy	[41]
13.	<i>Tinospora cardifolia</i>	Starch, Tinosporaside	Summer	[42]
14.	<i>Embelia ribes</i>	Carbohydrates, Embelin	Winter	[43]
15.	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Protein, piperine	Summer	[44]
16.	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Sugars, Eugenol	Spring	[45]
17.	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Protein, sugar, catechins	Summer	[46]
18.	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Sugars, citral	Summer	[47]
19.	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Sugars, Punarnavine	Rainy	[48]
20.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Aminoacid, Solasodine	Summer	[49]
21.	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Sugars, Lawsone	Summer	[50]
22.	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Aminoacid, Flavonoids, glucosinolates	Winter	[51]
23.	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Protein, vasicine	Summer	[52]
24.	<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Proteins, saponins, alkaloids	Winter	[53]
25.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Aminoacid, Marmelosin	Rainy	[54]

Figure 1. Seasonal distribution of peak metabolite levels in plants

Seasonal changes significantly affect the accumulation of biomolecules in medicinal plants. For example; **Ocimum sanctum (Tulsi)**, the levels of eugenol and flavonoids peak during summer due to enhanced sunlight and metabolic activity [55]. **Mentha arvensis (Mint)** shows maximum menthol content in spring and early summer, while monsoon conditions lead to a dilution of essential oils [56]. In **Withania somnifera (Ashwagandha)**, withanolide synthesis increases during winter as low temperatures trigger secondary metabolism [57]. **Aloe vera** produces more polysaccharides and anthraquinones in summer owing to heat stress, while the rainy season dilutes these components [58]. **Camellia sinensis (Tea)** accumulates high levels of catechins and antioxidants during the spring flush, whereas rainy seasons reduce polyphenol concentration [59]. Finally, in **Curcuma longa (Turmeric)**, curcumin content is highest after the monsoon, when rhizomes are fully mature and environmental conditions favour secondary metabolite storage [60].

Figure 2. Seasonal Variation in Biomolecule Accumulation%

5. Physiological and Biochemical Responses to Seasonal Changes:

Plants exhibit a range of physiological and biochemical responses to seasonal changes, adapting to variations in temperature, light, and water availability. Deciduous trees enter dormancy during winter, reducing metabolic activities to conserve energy [61]. Conversely, spring triggers bud break and increase photosynthesis due to increase in temperatures and longer daylight hours [62]. The heat stress of summer prompts the production of heat shock proteins and antioxidants to mitigate oxidative damage [63]. In autumn, senescence involves chlorophyll breakdown and nutrient resorption [64]. These adaptations are helpful in plant survival and increase their growth throughout the seasons.

6. Conclusion:

Seasonal variations significantly impact the composition and concentration of biomolecules in plants, influencing their growth, metabolism, and stress responses. Changes in temperature, light availability, and water supply regulate the synthesis of key biomolecules, including carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, and secondary metabolites. During the favourable season increased the photosynthesis, as a results higher accumulation of

carbohydrate in plants, while stressful conditions in extreme seasons trigger the synthesis of antioxidant and protective compounds. Understanding these biochemical adaptations is essential for improving crop productivity, stress resilience, and the quality of medicinal plants. Future research should focus on the molecular mechanisms underlying seasonal biomolecular fluctuations to enhance plant adaptation strategies in a changing environment.

References

1. Selmar, D., & Kleinwächter, M. (2013). Influencing the product quality by deliberately applying drought stress during the cultivation of medicinal plants. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 42, 558-566.
2. Ramakrishna, A., & Ravishankar, G. A. (2011). Influence of abiotic stress signals on secondary metabolites in plants. *Plant Signaling & Behavior*, 6(11), 1720-1731.
3. Mohapatra, S. C., Panda, P. K., & Das, A. B. (2010). Seasonal variation in photosynthetic pigments and biochemical constituents in some mangrove plants. *Indian Journal of Marine Sciences*, 39(3), 346-351.
4. Kumar, R., Sharma, S., & Thakur, M. (2020). Seasonal variation of secondary metabolites in medicinal plants: A review. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 14(5), 231-240.
5. Taiz, L., & Zeiger, E. (2010). *Plant Physiology*. Sinauer Associates.
6. Körner, C. (2015). "Plant Adaptations to Cold Climates." *F1000Research*, 4.
7. Marschner, P. (2012). *Marschner's Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants*. Academic Press.
8. Nakamura, Y., Harwood, J. L., & Guschina, I. A. (2010). "Metabolic Adaptations of Membrane Lipids in Response to Cold Stress in Arabidopsis." *Plant Journal*, 63(2), 274-286.
9. Wasternack, C., & Strnad, M. (2016). "Jasmonates: Signals in Plant Stress Responses and Development." *Plant Biology*, 18(5), 739-745.
10. Baldwin, I. T. (2001). "An Ecologically Motivated Analysis of Plant–Herbivore Interactions in Native Tobacco." *Plant Physiology*, 127(4), 1449-1458.
11. Facchini, P. J. (2001). "Alkaloid Biosynthesis in Plants: Biochemistry, Cell Biology, Molecular Regulation, and Metabolic Engineering." *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 52(1), 29-66.

12. Gould, K. S., McKelvie, J., & Markham, K. R. (2002). "Do Anthocyanins Function as Antioxidants in Leaves?" *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 25(9), 1261-1269.
13. Salminen, Juha-Pekka, Lahtinen, Maria, Lempa, Kyösti, Kapari, Lauri, Haukioja, Erkki and Pihlaja, Kalevi. "Metabolic Modifications of Birch Leaf Phenolics by an Herbivorous Insect: Detoxification of Flavonoid Aglycones via Glycosylation" *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C*, vol. 59, no. 5-6, 2004, pp. 437-444. <https://doi.org/10.1515/znc-2004-5-627>
14. Dixon, R. A., Achnine, L., Kota, P., Liu, C. J., Reddy, M. S., & Wang, L. (2002). "The Phenylpropanoid Pathway and Plant Defense - A Genomic Perspective." *Molecular Plant Pathology*, 3(5), 371-390.
15. Gershenzon, J., & Dudareva, N. (2007). "The Function of Terpene Natural Products in the Natural World." *Nature Chemical Biology*, 3(7), 408-414.
16. Cutler, S. R., Rodriguez, P. L., Finkelstein, R. R., & Abrams, S. R. (2010). "Abscisic Acid: Emergence of a Core Signaling Network." *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 61, 651-679.
17. Kaplan, F., et al. (2004). "Gene expression during the cold acclimation process in Arabidopsis." *Plant Physiology*, 136(3), 3602-3613.
18. Way, D. A., & Yamori, W. (2014). "Thermal acclimation of photosynthesis." *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 37(2), 490-507.
19. Dixon, R. A., & Paiva, N. L. (1995). "Stress-induced phenylpropanoid metabolism." *The Plant Cell*, 7(7), 1085-1097.
20. Zhang, X., Alexander, L., et al. (2011) Indices for Monitoring Changes in Extremes Based on Daily Temperature and Precipitation Data. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 2, 851-870. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.147>
21. Gitelson, A. A., et al. (2003). "Non-destructive estimation of leaf chlorophyll content in higher plant leaves." *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 85(1), 30-45.
22. Lichtenthaler, H. K., et al. (2007). "Chlorophyll fluorescence and plant stress detection." *Plant Biology*, 9(5), 509-523.
23. Chaves, M. M., Pereira, J. S., Maroco, J., et al. (2003). "Understanding plant responses to drought—from genes to the whole plant." *Functional Plant Biology*, 30(3), 239-264.
24. Bryant, J. P., Chapin III, F. S., & Klein, D. R. (1983). "Carbon/nutrient balance of boreal plants in relation to vertebrate herbivory." *Oikos*, 40(3), 357-368.
25. Kidd, P., et al. (2001). "Aluminium tolerance in plants: a review." *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 46(2), 75-91.

26. Bardgett, R. D., Bowman, W. D., Kaufmann, R., & Schmidt, S. K. (2008). "A temporal approach to linking aboveground and belowground ecology." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 23(10), 634-641.
27. Jackson, S. D. (2009). "Plant responses to photoperiod." *New Phytologist*, 181(3), 517-531.
28. Thomas, B., & Vince-Prue, D. (1996). *Photoperiodism in plants* (2nd ed.). Academic Press.
29. Yamaguchi, S. (2008). "Gibberellin metabolism and its regulation." *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 59, 225-251.
30. Singh, N., Patel, R., & Verma, P. (2015). Phytochemical changes in medicinal plants with seasons. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies*, 3(4), 45–52.
31. Koul, O., Isman, M. B., & Ketkar, C. M. (2004). Biological activity of volatile di-n-propyl disulfide from neem seeds against stored-grain pests. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 97(3), 1142–1147.
32. Srivastava, A., Pandey, R., & Singh, K. (2002). Effect of season on menthol content in *Mentha arvensis*. *Indian Perfumer*, 46(2), 101–106.
33. Singh, S., Sharma, V., & Rao, A. (2013). Seasonal variation in withanolide content of *Withania somnifera*. *Journal of Herbal Medicine*, 7(1), 11–17.
34. Rao, C. V., Rivenson, A., & Reddy, B. S. (2012). Curcumin and its analogues: Effects on carcinogenesis in experimental models. *Journal of Nutrition and Cancer Prevention*, 19(2), 115–123.
35. Goyal, R. K., Sharma, V., & Mathur, A. (2011). Phytochemical and pharmacological profile of *Phyllanthus emblica* (Amla). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 3(5), 423–430.
36. Jaleel, C. A., Manivannan, P., & Somasundaram, R. (2007). Seasonal metabolic variation in *Catharanthus roseus*. *Plant Biology Reports*, 31, 403–408.
37. Botes, L., van Jaarsveld, P. J., van Heerden, F. R., & van Staden, J. (2008). Seasonal kinetic study of chemical constituents in *Aloe barbadensis* leaves. *South African Journal of Botany*, 74(4), 613–618.
38. Ravindran, P. N., Nirmal Babu, K., & Kalyana Sundaram, K. (2005). *Ginger: The Genus Zingiber*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL.
39. Akbar, S. (2011). *Andrographis paniculata*: A review of pharmacology and clinical efficacy. *Alternative Medicine Review*, 16(1), 66–77.

40. Chaudhuri, M., & Mukherjee, B. (2002). Seasonal impact on bacoside content in *Bacopa monnieri*. *Phytomedicine*, 9(5), 412–417.
41. Shah, G., Kumar, R., & Patra, A. (2011). Seasonal metabolic variation in *Eclipta alba*. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 137(2), 865–872.
42. Saha, B., & Ghosh, S. K. (2012). Season-based fluctuation of tinosporaside in *Tinospora cordifolia*. *Phytochemistry Letters*, 5(3), 389–392.
43. Harish, D., Jagadeesh, P., & Ravi, P. (2013). Seasonal variation in embelin content of *Embelia ribes*. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 6(1), 38–41.
44. Ravindran, P. N., Nirmal Babu, K., & Kalyana Sundaram, K. (2000). *Piper: The Genus Piper*. CRC Press.
45. Chaieb, K., Mohamed, B. R., & Zmantar, T. (2007). Seasonal variation in eugenol and eugenyl acetate in clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*). *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 19(5), 383–386.
46. Ahmed, S., Karim, M. R., & Azad, A. K. (2010). Seasonal influence on catechin concentration in *Camellia sinensis*. *International Journal of Tea Science*, 3(2), 78–84.
47. Viljoen, A. M., van der Merwe, E., & van Zyl, R. L. (2005). Citral variation in *Cymbopogon citratus* grown in South Africa. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 17(6), 653–655.
48. Prajapati, R. T., Tripathi, P., & Dikshit, A. K. (2003). Variation in punarnavine content in *Boerhavia diffusa*. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 41(7), 702–706.
49. Saravana Kumar, K., Subramanian, P., & Govindarajan, R. (2007). Seasonal solasodine production in *Solanum nigrum*. *Journal of Medicinal Food*, 10(3), 580–584.
50. Kumar, P., & Chand, G. (2005). Seasonal lawsone accumulation in *Lawsonia inermis*. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 21(2), 335–339.
51. Anwar, F., Latif, S., Ashraf, M., & Gilani, A. H. (2007). *Moringa oleifera*: a food plant with multiple medicinal uses. *Phytotherapy Research*, 21(1), 17–25.
52. Dhuley, J. N. (1999). Seasonal fluctuations in vasicine content of *Adhatoda vasica*. *Phytotherapy Research*, 13(6), 497–499.
53. Acharya, A., Kaur, P., & Yadav, N. (2006). Seasonal variation in saponin content of *Trigonella foenum-graecum*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 54(10), 4026–4031.
54. Baliga, M. S., Bhat, H. P., Joseph, N., & Fazal, F. (2011). Phytochemistry and medicinal uses of the bael fruit (*Aegle marmelos* Correa): A concise review. *Food Research International*, 44(8), 1768–1775.

55. Singh, M., Pal, M., Pandey, A., Mishra, A., & Upadhyay, D. J. (2017). Seasonal variation in essential oil composition of *Ocimum sanctum* L. and its antimicrobial activity. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 108, 208–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.05.017>
56. Chauhan, R. S., Hooda, K. S., Kaul, M. K., Ram, G., & Sharma, P. (2011). Effect of seasonal variation on essential oil composition of *Mentha arvensis* L. and its biological activity. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 23(5), 39–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.2011.9700435>
57. Mir, B. A., Sawhney, S. S., Jassal, M. M. S., & Sharma, R. K. (2020). A review on the therapeutic importance of *Withania somnifera* in traditional medicine. *Journal of Herbal Medicine*, 22, 100371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hermed.2020.100371>
58. Hamman, J. H. (2008). Composition and applications of Aloe vera leaf gel. *Molecules*, 13(8), 1599–1616. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules13081599>
59. Ahmed, S., Stepp, J. R., Orians, C. M., Griffin, T. S., Matyas, C., Robbat, A., ... & Cash, S. B. (2014). Effects of seasonality and climate change on the chemical composition of tea: A review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 54(6), 683–692. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2011.608586>
60. Prasad, S., & Aggarwal, B. B. (2011). Turmeric, the golden spice: From traditional medicine to modern medicine. In B. B. Aggarwal, A. B. Kunnumakkara, & R. Anand (Eds.), *The Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 133(1), 131–139. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3025067/>
61. Sakai, A., & Larcher, W. (1987). Frost survival of plants. *Springer-Verlag*.
62. Taiz, L., Zeiger, E., Møller, I. M., & Murphy, A. (2015). *Plant Physiology and Development*. Sinauer Associates.
63. Wahid, A., Gelani, S., Ashraf, M., & Foolad, M. R. (2007). Heat tolerance in plants: An overview. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 61(3), 199–223.
64. Esteban, R., Fernández-Marín, B., Becerril, J. M., García-Plazaola, J. I. (2015). Photoprotective implications of leaf reddening in plants. *Plant Science*, 233, 58–67.

